

CyberHeraclius: Cyber Defence Evaluation Methodology

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Abstract—Security evaluation remains a critical challenge in cybersecurity, especially with the growing complexity of systems like cloud and IoT environments. This paper introduces CyberHeraclius, a novel methodology for evaluating the security of modern computer networks. The process begins with automated asset mapping and the collection of public Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI) from MITRE’s CVE, CWE, and CAPEC repositories, as well as Metasploit. To address CTI limitations, such as false positives and coverage gaps, automated penetration testing is used to verify actual vulnerabilities. The validated results feed into a Medieval Castle-based security model, which assesses system resilience based on component composition. CTI risk metrics are then integrated with the model’s aggregation formulas to quantify overall system risk. CyberHeraclius is part of the SecOPERA Platform, which supports secure continuous integration and deployment (CI/CD) pipelines for system developers.

Keywords—security assessment, penetration testing, CPE, resilience, risk management

I. INTRODUCTION

In today’s interconnected world, modern computerized solutions, ranging from mobile applications and cloud services to smart devices and IoT technologies, are deeply integrated into everyday life [1]. While these advancements offer significant convenience and productivity, they also increase exposure to cyber threats [2]. With sensitive data constantly in transit or stored online, robust cybersecurity measures are essential to protect individuals, organizations, and critical infrastructure.

The ICT community has responded with coordinated efforts to identify vulnerabilities, develop public repositories like CVE [3], and promote Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI) sharing [4]-[5]. However, securing complex systems such as cloud and IoT environments remains challenging due to their dynamic, distributed nature [6]-[7]. Integrating security into Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) pipelines is particularly difficult, requiring accurate vulnerability detection with minimal false positives and false negatives.

This paper presents CyberHeraclius, a novel security evaluation methodology inspired by Byzantine Emperor Heraclius, who defended his empire through regional fortifications. CyberHeraclius begins by modeling system assets, covering cloud, IoT, and embedded systems. Automated tools are used to: i) map and analyze the infrastructure, and ii) collect CTI from sources like CVE [3], CWE [8], CAPEC [9], and Metasploit [10]. Since CTI may

include false positives (unexploitable elements) and miss unknown vulnerabilities (false negatives), automated penetration testing is performed to verify which vulnerabilities are actually exploitable.

This twofold process confirms secure components (reducing FPs) and uncovers unseen weaknesses (reducing FNs). The validated results feed into a risk assessment methodology based on the Medieval Castle model [11]-[12], which factors in system composition and threat impact. A prototype implementation focusing on network-level evaluation has been integrated into the SecOPERA Platform, and tested in two pilot cases: i) a smart motorbike system, and ii) an IoT solution for irrigation and waste monitoring.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews related work in asset modeling, CTI, and security evaluation. Section 3 introduces the CyberHeraclius methodology. Section 4 presents implementation details and use cases. Section 5 concludes the paper and discusses future work.

II. RELATED WORK

A. The Current Threat Landscape

The threat landscape for modern computerized systems is increasingly dynamic, driven by the widespread adoption of cloud services, IoT, mobile technologies, and AI [13]-[14]. Cybercriminals and state-sponsored actors exploit a wide array of vectors, including ransomware, supply-chain breaches, and zero-day vulnerabilities. Advanced Persistent Threats (APTs) are now targeting critical sectors such as energy, finance, and healthcare. The growing complexity and interconnectedness of digital ecosystems have significantly expanded the attack surface, making comprehensive security more challenging. Moreover, the use of third-party services, decentralized infrastructures, and remote work has introduced new vulnerabilities, while attackers employ automation, social engineering, and AI to conduct highly targeted attacks.

Big Data technologies enhance cybersecurity by enabling the real-time analysis of vast datasets to detect, prevent, and predict threats [15]. Using AI and machine learning, Big Data tools can correlate CTI, logs, and behavioral data to identify anomalies and system misconfigurations. These insights support proactive defense strategies and improve CI/CD pipelines by embedding early-stage threat detection during system design and testing.

B. Asset Modeling and Correlation with Cyber Threats

Asset modeling involves identifying system components (assets), their properties, and interactions – often a prerequisite for certifications such as ISO-19770. Modern approaches aim to address dynamic environments like cloud and IoT systems. Graph-based models, as highlighted in [16], visualize dependencies and potential attack paths, though their reliance on predefined patterns limits responsiveness to novel or zero-day threats.

Ontology-based models provide a structured and interoperable way to define assets and relationships [17]. While effective for standardization and cross-platform integration, they often struggle to adapt to rapidly evolving environments like microservices or virtualized infrastructure.

A critical step in asset modeling is asset enumeration, which catalogs all hardware, software, and services in a system. The Common Platform Enumeration (CPE) standard [18] enables consistent asset identification, supporting correlation with vulnerability databases like CVE [19]. Tools such as Nmap, OpenVAS, OpenSCAP, and cloud-native solutions (e.g., AWS Config, Azure Security Center) help automate asset discovery and vulnerability scanning [20]. However, maintaining accuracy in dynamic and ephemeral environments remains a key challenge.

C. CTI Incorporation and Implications

International organizations actively document and analyze cybersecurity issues in software and hardware. Key initiatives include: i) CVE and CWE by MITRE, cataloging known software and hardware vulnerabilities; ii) NVD by NIST, which evaluates CVE criticality using the CVSS scoring system [21]; iii) CAPEC, documenting known attack patterns; and iv) Metasploit, offering real-world exploit code. CWE scoring uses CWSS [22], and all repositories typically utilize CPE identifiers for consistent asset classification and cross-referencing (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Public CTI repositories and their correlation.

CVE-based analysis is a widely accepted approach in risk management and often a requirement for security certification (e.g., ISO, NIST). Studies show that reported CVEs can remain unpatched for over 5 years [23]. However, challenges include false positives (non-exploitable vulnerabilities due to defenses) and false negatives (undetected zero-days). Moreover, asset tagging via CPE is sometimes inaccurate, and CVE entries may be delayed.

Recent research explores combining CPE-based CVE aggregation with CVSS metrics to quantify digital risk [24]. However, most approaches assess vulnerabilities individually, overlooking how one vulnerability can facilitate the exploitation of another. To address this, some studies use attack graphs [25] to analyze vulnerability interactions. Nonetheless, limitations include the need for manual system

modeling, user expertise, and the lack of topology-aware risk estimation.

D. Security Evaluation Approaches

Security evaluation during system design increasingly follows Security-by-Design principles, integrating protection into the Secure Software Development Lifecycle (SDLC). This includes setting security requirements, conducting architectural risk assessments, and evaluating design decisions using models such as OWASP SAMM and CLASP [26]. While effective, these methods demand considerable resources and close coordination between developers and security teams.

Threat modeling is another core approach, helping to identify risks early. Frameworks like STRIDE and DREAD, along with tools such as Microsoft’s Threat Modeling Tool, provide structured ways to anticipate and prioritize threats [27]. However, these models may struggle to capture all threats in complex, rapidly evolving systems.

Attack surface analysis further enhances security by identifying all potential external access points, including APIs and interfaces. Tools like Microsoft’s Attack Surface Analyzer and OWASP’s Detector assist in quantifying exposure [28] but are challenged by the dynamic nature of cloud and microservice environments, which require continuous monitoring.

Lastly, the “medieval castle” analogy [11]-[12] underpins the widely adopted Defense-in-Depth (DiD) strategy, where layered defenses (e.g., firewalls, IDS, encryption) provide redundancy and resilience. This model aligns with established standards such as the NIST Cybersecurity Framework and ISO/IEC 27001, emphasizing multi-layered protection across digital infrastructures.

E. Quantitative Analysis

The CyberHeraclius project aims to deliver a practical and fine-grained methodology for risk management and security assessment in modern systems, addressing limitations of existing methods. It begins with automated asset discovery, using a network mapper to detect system topology, open ports, and running services—including those unknown to the user. Additionally, system developers can deploy OpenSCAP at each node to collect detailed digital fingerprints and retrieve CPE identifiers. These are used to build a structured Asset Model representing system components and their interrelations.

Next, public Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI) is aggregated per asset. For each CPE, relevant CVEs and their CVSS scores are collected, along with available exploits from Metasploit. CVEs are mapped to CWEs, which are further associated with attack modes and CAPEC patterns, enriching the threat landscape analysis.

Automated assessments are then executed on the live system to eliminate false positives and uncover previously unrecognized vulnerabilities – particularly in assets lacking valid CPEs (e.g., custom software). This step enhances the accuracy of the CTI-driven analysis.

Finally, a hierarchical risk evaluation is performed, incorporating system topology and asset interdependencies. By applying the Medieval Castle model to the Asset Model

Fig. 2. CyberHeraklius operation.

and attack surface data, the approach provides a composition-aware risk estimation. The process can be scheduled periodically, enabling continuous security evaluation and adaptation to evolving threat trends.

Table I presents a comparative analysis of CyberHeraklius against established tools, demonstrating its advancement in combining automated asset discovery, CTI correlation, vulnerability validation, and systemic risk calculation.

TABLE I. COMPARISON OF SECURITY ASSESSMENT TOOLS

Features	CyberHeraklius	NMap	OpenVAS	OpenSCAP
Asset identification	Y	P	P	P
Asset modeling	Y	N	N	N
CTI collection	Y	Y	Y	Y
Removal of FPs	Y	N	Y	N
Penetration testing	Y	N	Y	N
Estimation of risk per asset	Y	N	Y	N
Estimation of aggregated risk of system	Y	N	N	N

*(Y)es, (N)o, (P)artially

III. CYBERHERACLIUS METHODOLOGY

This Section presents the CyberHeraklius solution. Initially, the Asset Model is described for defining a system and decompose it into hardware and software layers. Thereupon, public CTI can be collected for all system assets based on valid CPE IDs. Afterwards, assessment tests are performed for all assets to enhance the accuracy of CTI, followed by the risk evaluation process. Figure 2 depicts the overall process.

A. Asset Model

The Asset Model is a fundamental element for the establishment of the Asset Inventory for a system, keeping an abstraction level that is understandable by the average user while enabling the application of a sufficient security

assessment afterwards (subsection 3.D). Therefore, an asset can belong in one of the following categories:

- **Physical asset:** the actual physical hardware
- **Hardware asset:** the hardware layer, which can either match with a physical asset or can be virtual, i.e., the flavor part of a Virtual Machine (VM).
- **System Software asset:** the operating system and system software that interplays with the underlying hardware and installed applications.
- **Application Software asset:** the applications installed within a System Software asset.

A Hardware asset can contain System Software assets, and each System Software asset can contain Application Software assets. In order to also model virtualization, it is defined that an Application Software asset can also contain Hardware and System Software assets. For example, Virtual Box can be defined as Application Software that encapsulates pairs of Hardware and System Software assets, i.e., the hardware architecture and operating system of VMs.

Henceforth, the user can start defining assets for a system. Also, a series of options are supported to automate part of the decomposition process. The user can provide a Software Bill of Materials (SBOM) for a software solution that wants to analyze. Then, the SBOM elements are mapped to related assets (mostly Application Software assets). Also, the user can deploy his/her solution on an actual system or testbed. Thereupon, the user can run OpenSCAP in order to discover the installed applications within an operating system. Moreover, the user can run network mapping in order to identify the running services within a machine. This option is also the indicative choice in cases where a third-party solution is integrated in the system and is analyzed as a “black-box”, with the user/developer having no control over the inner structure of this asset.

User interaction is required in this semi-automated process. Apart from activating the right tools, the developer might need to fill missing information, like CPEs that are not mentioned in the SBOM or provide the network IPs where the deployed system is running.

Also, assets are integrated and combined in order to form the overall system. Therefore, the composition states of the Medieval Castle model are followed, as they are described in subsection 3.D below. In short, assets can be in the same architectural layer, in subsequent layers, or in parallel ones.

B. CTI Search

After the aforementioned mapping of the system's assets, public CTI can be collected. For each asset with valid CPE record, a list of CVEs can be disclosed. Thereupon, the Metasploit framework supports search of runnable exploits based on a CVE identifier. Also, a CVE contains a series of related CWEs. Based on each CWE identifier, CAPECs are collected, which are describing how the CWE (and subsequently the relevant CVEs) can be exploited.

Several services have been implemented for this process, which will be provided as open-source under this repository in GitHub [30]. These include services to: i) Retrieve a CVE record based on a CPE or CVE identifier, from the NVD repository, which also includes the risk evaluation metrics of the CVSS methodology, ii) Retrieve a CWE based on a CWE identifier, from the MITRE repository, which also includes the risk evaluation metrics of the CWSS methodology, as well as retrieve the CWEs of a CVE, iii) Retrieve a CAPEC based on a CAPEC identifier, from the MITRE repository, as well as retrieve the CAPECs of a CWE, and iv) Retrieve potential exploits based on a CVE identifier, from the Metasploit framework. As mentioned before, the CTI collection is a fully automated process.

C. Assessment Tests

The SecOPERA Platform supports a wide series of tests in order to assess the actual security level of a system, covering: i) Hardware, ii) Software, iii) Network, and iv) Cognitive (ML) levels. For this paper, we concentrate our research and application of CyberHeraclius on the *network layer*.

Dynamic vulnerability assessment enhances the CyberHeraclius solution by enabling real-time detection and assessment of vulnerabilities. This module is essential for initiating dynamic network testing assessments for examined systems.

The presented penetration testing toolkit implements this dynamic vulnerability assessment by adding some more advanced functionality, concerning recording and analyzing the networking services. For this preliminary version, the toolkit assists the user to: i) map a deployed network and record it in an assessment inventory (e.g., network hosts, ports' status, running services, etc.), ii) search for existing exploits of each identified CVE, which a penetration tester can examine, iii) evaluate the login services (e.g., password-cracking), and examine if the services are vulnerable to DoS attacks.

The goal of this toolkit is to automate, in a fine-grained way, the network assessment elements of the SecOPERA solution. The process starts by mapping a network under examination. The Nmap solution is utilized underneath. This is an important step for a developer, who deploys a network and wants to show evidence that his/her implementation complies with the designated design. The main outcomes of this operation include a record of the running hosts, their ports and the related running services. Also, for each service, the relevant CPE is identified. These pieces of information can be

used to automatically update the Asset Model and perform the aforementioned vulnerability assessments.

Thereupon, for each discovered threat, the toolkit can search in CTI repositories to examine if there are existing exploits or patterns of attack. Apart from offering descriptive and technical information, such repositories also provide an indication of how easily each threat can be exploited, often

Fig. 3. The fundamental structure of the medieval castle approach includes various configurations.

including examples of actual runnable exploits. Once all these pieces of CTI have been collected, the penetration tester evaluates the more severe threats (i.e., examining exploits that can easily or even automatically be launched) and updates the network accordingly.

For each mapped service in the network, the toolkit can also launch (automatically or on-demand) login cracking operations. The Hydra password cracking tool is used for this goal. The system evaluates wherever accounts with weak or default credentials have been assigned in the network. The user can also define his/her own password patterns that will be tested (e.g., secrets that are using the organization's name as a prefix).

The toolkit is deployed in the SecOPERA backend platform as a VM, where this solution and the underlying technologies have been installed. APIs are exposed and the user can access this functionality through the graphical interface of the SecOPERA Hub Dashboard. The user mainly provides the range of Internet Protocol (IP) addresses that will be examined, and the overall information is visualized in various screens, as well as in a unified report. All pieces of knowledge are stored in a local database.

D. Risk Evaluation

The medieval castle approach is a primary method used to evaluate the security of composed systems, where a system is conceptualized as a medieval castle equipped with security doors that serve as targets for attacks. An attack is considered successful if it breaches the doors and gains access to the "treasure room", which represents the assets being protected by the security mechanisms. The level of difficulty in penetrating the doors and reaching the treasure room indicates the system's security level. Each door corresponds to a security mechanism deployed in the system, and its ability to withstand attacks is measured using relevant metrics.

To determine the system's overall security, the security levels of individual components are assessed, and the total protection is calculated based on composition rules. Figure 3 illustrates different configurations of system composition under the medieval castle approach. Circles symbolize protection mechanisms, while the dashes denote corresponding doors (attack points), with the assets depicted as the black center of each circle. Let d represent the castle's overall protection level. Castle Figure 3A shows a basic setup where the assets are guarded by a single door, making the

castle's security equal to that of the door's defense level. In configurations with two doors (d_{max} and d_{min}), where d_{max} is more robust than d_{min} , Castle Figure 3B positions the doors at the same layer, allowing simultaneous attacks on both. Here, the security level is determined by the weaker door, as compromising d_{max} may reduce the protection at d_{min} .

Castle Figure 3C arranges the two doors sequentially, requiring attackers to bypass both to reach the assets. This configuration offers stronger security than Figure 3B and at least matches the defense of d_{max} . In Figure 3D, there are two separate castles, and attackers must choose one target. An attack is considered successful if it compromises at least one of the protected resources. However, the distance between the castles prevents simultaneous attacks, implying that attackers can only focus on one type of attack at a time (e.g., a DoS attack on a web service or a password guessing attack on an authentication service). The range between d_{min} and d_{max} determines the overall security in this scenario.

In total, three fundamental composition operations are defined:

- AND-operation: $0 \leq d \leq d_{min}$
- OR-operation: $d_{max} \leq d \leq 1$
- MEAN-operation: $d_{min} \leq d \leq d_{max}$

Medieval castle analysis can also be applied to more complex compositions, breaking down castles with various door configurations. Using fundamental composition principles, attack trees can model the effort required to breach the system from its outer defense layers. For more details concerning the foundation of the medieval castle methodology refer to the primary article [11], and for a complete application example on an IoT system refer to our previous work in [12].

IV. DEVELOPMENT & EVALUATION

A. Implementation Details

The CyberHeraklius is deployed as a dedicated VM within the SecOPERA Platform. Services are provided for each underlying component (i.e., asset mapping, CTI search, penetration testing toolkit, and risk evaluation) and the user can use them via the SecOPERA Hub Dashboard. The current version of the penetration testing toolkit can analyze the networking infrastructure of a piloting system, which is accessible from the SecOPERA Platform end.

For the implementation of CyberHeraklius, a Kali Linux VM is used where Metasploit is pre-installed. The CyberHeraklius back-end components are implemented in Python as Flask services. The front-end and the Graphical User Interface (GUI) are implemented in Angular. Both back-end and front-end are dockerized. The overall assessment results are stored in a local relational database with MariaDB.

For Asset Modeling, the analyst can activate the network mapping service and scan a network asset. If the user has access to the examined node (e.g., not a black-box analysis) and requires more detailed results, he/she can run an extended OpenSCAP agent within the machine to map the internal assets of the network component. Thereupon, the CTI search is implemented based on the services that are mentioned in subsection 3B and the results are stored in the database.

For the purposes of penetration testing, a series of tests was developed in order to assess whether an examined network

asset is vulnerable to i) *port scanning*, ii) *login cracking*, iii) *DoS*, or iv) supports communication protocols with *outdated cryptographic algorithms*. If an asset is found to be vulnerable, relevant CTI findings are reported based on the CVE format. These CVEs have been correlated in advance with specific CWEs and CAPECs. If an asset is not vulnerable, then information about the test is recorded as a security guarantee and related public CTI is removed as FP.

The risk is calculated automatically after every update in the knowledge base (as described in the subsection 3D). Therefore, the penetration testing module systematically analyses the network layer to identify exploitable vulnerabilities, allowing for repeated cycles of patching until a satisfactory level of security and risk mitigation is achieved.

B. Piloting Evaluation

A *preliminary version of CyberHeraklius* has been evaluated under the first trials on testbeds of the two SecOPERA pilots. This includes the evaluation of networking for an in-vehicle system on motor bikes and an IoT infrastructure for water irrigation.

CyberHeraklius tries to facilitate the user in recording the network topology and performing automatically, in an easy and fine-grained manner, a series of penetration testing elements. Related outputs were incorporated in a report that provided evidence concerning the network mapping and wherever it complies with the desired network that the designer requested. The report also documented wherever the identified vulnerabilities from the first phases of network (or other) assessment are exploitable or if there are user accounts deployed with default or weak credentials, as well as if some services are supporting weak or update cryptography or whether there are no firewall rules to mitigate DoS attacks or failed login attempts. Based on these findings, the assets were updated and reassessed until the required level of protection was achieved.

Concerning performance, several of the reported operations, like penetration testing, is typical quite time consuming (ranging from some minutes for port scanning to even several days for login cracking) [31]-[33]. Thus, many services are parallelized to enhance performance, such as network mapping, the collection of CWEs for a CVE and CAPECs for each CWE, as well as the penetration test for port scanning and login cracking. The time for CTI search can be further minimized if all CVE, CWE, CAPEC, and Metasploit repositories have been retrieved in advance and the search requests are served locally in the database. This option is also supported by this implementation.

V. CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

Assessment of the cyber-risk and the security level of a system is a quite complex and time-consuming process. This paper presents a relevant solution, called CyberHeraclius. The proposal exhibits promising results concerning automated or semi-automated modeling of a system and collection of accurate CTI in the network layer. Thereupon, the security of individual components, as well as for the composed system as a whole, can be estimated. The result utilizes well-accepted risk metrics from public CTI initiatives (e.g., MITRE, FIRST, and NIST) and an understandable and logical composition approach (i.e., Medieval Castle). A preliminary implementation has been incorporated under the EU funded

project SecOPERA, while some open-source parts are shared publicly under this work.

As future extensions, it is considered the inclusion of assessment tests for the hardware, software, and cognitive layers of SecOPERA. Moreover, the extensive evaluation under the two SecOPERA pilots is planned for the next phase.

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